

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: A BOOSTER OR A DEPRESSOR OF HUMAN COGNITIVE DEVELOPMENT?

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13765713

Maria Nazaré Ribon Silva

Graduated in Portuguese Language and Literature. Master in Education from the IPLAC Institute - Cuba. Portuguese Language Teacher - permanent in the State Public School System - Espírito Santo. Currently, she works as a teacher of Specialized Educational Services - AEE. E-mail: nazareribonsilva@hotmail.com. Lattes CV: <http://lattes.cnpq.br/1143785802367605>

Sérgio Rodrigues de Souza

Pedagogue. Philosopher. Post-PhD. in Social Psychology. E-mail: srgrodriguesdesouza@gmail.com.

ABSTRACT

This essay addresses the topic of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and whether it works as a booster or a depressant for human cognitive development. Its scientific relevance is presented in the fact that it brings an open criticism to the conventionalism that has imposed itself in relation to the subject, preventing critical debate. Its social relevance is shown in the possibility of presenting to the public the extent of the reach of technology and the possibilities of manipulating it in favor of a very few. In the face of all technological advances, humanity cannot ignore that this has almost reached its peak, the creation of an autonomous, sensitive and perceptive machine, since, since the invention of the wheel, Man has made use of technology and, its advancement generates controversy and fear in society, this feeling that arises due to ignorance on the subject in question. However, it remains to be seen to what extent to consider these inventions as allies or threats to human cognition. The objective is to analyze whether Artificial Intelligence is an ally or a threat to the intellectual, affective and behavioral development of Man. To construct this essay, bibliographical research, analysis and synthesis were used. The creation of AI follows the principle that things will be solved more quickly and accurately, leaving humanity free to make decisions in other fields. It turns out that this is an obtuse thought, because situations do not occur in a linear way, much less the solution conditions, which often require detailed analysis and can even offer the option of non-intervention, a decision that would be impossible for an automaton, since it is programmed to act towards conflict resolution; not to analyze its ethical and psychological dimension and its impacts on the future of those involved.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence. Education. Human formation. Cognitive Development. Public policy.

**CONJECTURES ABOUT STUDENTS' COGNITIVE DEVELOPMENT AND
TECHNOLOGICAL ADVANCEMENT THROUGH ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE**

After the advent of the Second World War (1939-1945), humanity witnessed a technological evolution in industry, science, the technological field and society so significant that the poet Cassiano Ricardo (1895-1974) was already criticizing the possibility of technology advances to the point where God is replaced by machines. This thought was very well expressed in the text *Ladainha*, published in 1964:

Why reasoning, muscles, bones?
Automation, golden leisure.
The electronic brain, the mechanical muscle
Easier than a smile.
Why the heart?
The metal one will not make the man
More cordial, giving it an extra-corporeal rhythm?
Why raise your arm
To reap the fruit?
The machine will do it for us.
Why work in the countryside, in the city?
The machine will do it for us.
Why think,
Imagine?
The machine will do it for us.
Why make a poem?
The machine will do it for us.
Why climb Jacob's ladder?
The machine will do it for us.
Oh machine, pray for us (RICARDO, 1976, *sp.*).

The shock at a reality that was already emerging at that time can be understood as natural. However, the advancement and use of technology are so subtle and necessary in various areas of industry, transportation, education, security, communication, science and even housing, that society uses it automatically, often without thinking, as is the case with the use of the wheel. Someone only thinks about using a car wheel, for example, when it gets a flat tire. And from the wheel, many gears for the operation of more sophisticated machines were perfected. This marks the development and systematic and pragmatic application of its domestic use. Thus, it is natural that there is astonishment at the creation of Artificial Intelligence (AI), since humanity did not expect that, in the 21st century, all this could happen and, in view of this, it already envisions the possibilities of using this tool in various sectors, not only in industrial and even agricultural production, but in health, security and also in wars, as was the case in the War against Osama Bin Laden, in which the smart bombs, developed by the American arms industry

and used by the United States of America (USA) army, presented a modest margin of error of only 40%.

A more detailed observation already allows us to summarize how technological advances are being absorbed into the daily lives of millions of users without them realizing all the advances that the object undergoes over time, as is the case of the computer that, through its programming algorithms, already establishes a dialogue with the user when the questions appear on the screen: *Save* , *No Save* , *Cancel* . In this case, the computer's programming is prepared to respond to commands typed on the keyboard, already anticipating an action. Each key has a specific function. The computer is an automaton, responding only to external commands; however, in recent times, it has been realized that, behind the entire range of information available on the World Wide Web (Internet), there is an artificial intelligence, which can trace the user's profile and offer entertainment according to their taste. And this is happening without society noticing. Now with Google Assistant, it is possible to dictate commands through speech and receive the response through speech as well.

The accessibility function, also called assistive technology, is present in some machines and computers, which performs oral reading for students with visual impairments, such as dyslexia, for example. As well as other assistive technologies that help people with disabilities not only in accessing information, but also in routines such as eating, writing, among others. In this case, the use of technology is essential, as it makes life easier for this specific population, guaranteeing the broad right to learning.

In this same vein, it can be seen that the use of technology makes life easier for people who have lost limbs, such as arms and legs, through the use of mechanical hands and legs. There are situations in which these limbs are connected to the central nervous system with the help of electrodes, so that the individual can control, for example, the movements of their hands and fingers. There is exoskeleton training so that quadriplegics can stand and walk. Wheelchairs powered by electrodes connected to the wheelchair user's central nervous system, robotic hands that assist in surgeries, bomb disarming, and access to dangerous places such as the bottom of the sea, electrical cables, among others.

In the year 2000, Chaimowicz and Campos made the following statement:

Robots are beginning to be used in a wide range of activities, from disarming bombs and landmines to inspecting underwater telephone cables, repairs to nuclear power plants, space exploration, aerial surveillance of forests, among others. Robots are even playing an important role as guides in certain museums (CHAIMOWICZ and CAMPOS, 2000, sp).

Thus, robots began to be used on a large scale in different industrial sectors, in security, health, education, research, among others. However, in order for them to perform all these activities, they needed to be programmed by humans. The robot was [*and continues to be*] an automaton. In the meantime, the presence of robots in everyday life is so intense that it no longer causes so much surprise. However, development has been so significant during the last two decades that humans have created autonomous robots, that is, they do not need to be programmed, they think and create on their own. Given this situation, an uncertain future has unfolded before humanity's eyes, full of questions, among which the following can be highlighted: 'Who will program who?'

This is a type of concern that should not represent the cause of fear, because the robot's autonomy is limited by the programming it has; similar to man, whose wisdom is limited by his degree of knowledge and this, in turn, is restricted to the empirical experiences he has had.

A discreet look at the past allows us to make the following observation: that the successful, as always, will be benefited and untouchable, and the less favored will remain as they are or worse; because the invisible hands of power have always been used to manipulate and keep a legion of men trapped in poverty and ignorance. In this context, schools, churches, sports and culture were used as instruments of alienation and massification. The use of technology such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) could be further intensified as an instrument of control over individual and collective behavior. This can already be seen through access to networks: when a simple question is typed into the search platform, the answer is automatically answered on the computer screen, without the researcher needing to delve deeper into their reading, analysis and synthesis. This increasingly limits the practice of reading, research and comparisons between the different ideas of different authors.

The presence of AI in everyday life is so subtle that the user gradually uses it as if he were eating it; however, as he uses it, he can gradually be induced to be passive, an automaton, at the mercy of a favored few, as has been the case throughout human history. After all, since the creation of the wheel, the airplane and other inventions, everything has presented itself as dubious things and situations, sometimes tending towards good, sometimes towards evil. Wheels have favored the transportation of food, as they are also used to transport weapons of war. Airplanes are used to shorten distances between cities; but they were and are used to transport weapons and drop bombs on innocent people. Faced with this new reality, *who controls who ? Who will control who ?* Another question arises: 'If AI is autonomous, can the most favored and ill-intentioned politicians manipulate it to use it as they wish?' Only the future will bring this answer; However, if they control the entire population of a country endowed

with millions and millions of thinking neurons, injecting individualistic, biased and hateful ideologies through the denial of access to quality Culture and Education, with threats of death and even executions, imprisonment, deprivation of food, basic sanitation, diseases and much more, suddenly, in possession of some instrument, which can be used as a control key, they manage to alienate and massify and also turn off AI.

In 1991, Silva issued the following warning: “By placing the responsibility for political decisions and actions on the government, many educators remain kneeling and with their heads bowed, hoping that the results from above will be favorable to the educational and cultural issues of our people” (SILVA, 1991, p. 11). This type of statement is a provocation, a call for opinion makers, even under pressure, to free themselves from this control exercised by the State and adopt a praxis based on their point of view and knowledge; after all, they are authorities on the subject they teach and not mere *professionals* who sit behind a desk, in the air conditioning and who invent trends to keep the teacher *in line* and the people under control, in order to show their work to their superiors.

Today, control remains, when the government offers free textbooks and makes an unprecedented demand that teachers follow the curriculum guidelines, not as proposals, but as an imposition, since it disregards the reality in which the students are inserted and their prior knowledge; as a result, there is no learning. In this case, the school staff remains as instruments of manipulation and alienation. Added to this issue, it is possible to raise other problems such as, for example, the induction of unbridled consumption and waste linked to the mass media. In this sense, consumption ranges from gambling to alcohol that cause addictions and social problems, to an alienated culture that compromises intellectual and critical development. Thus, the individual carries with him the vices that fill his existence with a spirit of servitude and fear.

Here, it can be said that access to Culture, Art, Science and a dignified existence promotes spiritual well-being, intellectual and critical development of the population and that these can be achieved through the provision of quality education. However, the thinking people represent a threat to those in power and, thus, everything remains the same, always more of the same. The composer Zé Ramalho summed it all up in these verses: “Outside it is a comfortable time, the surveillance takes care of the normal” (RAMAHLLO, 1979, sp). The way things are going, *cattle* and the *lives of cattle* will not be favored by any benefits that AI can bring, because it is the system that chooses who lives and how they live. Who had the money to buy a computer three decades ago and even today? Who has the money to buy an automated robot today and in a few years? As Cunha (1997) argues, part of this situation can be alleviated when the teacher training course “gives the opportunity to inquire, research, create, recreate, so that literature

comes to have a truly recreational and aesthetic function and, therefore, a social and renewing one among the activities of children and adolescents” (CUNHA, 1997, p. 18).

All of this needs to be rethought; since providing children with screens at a very young age promises to further compromise the cognitive capacity of future adults. In a way, this is a reflection of families who are also victims of an alienating system that does not encourage them to read, listen to quality music, research and write, and express strong opinions on politics, sports, culture, religion and science. After all, when they were in school, their parents were also denied access to reading, writing and arithmetic, since they were forced to memorize in order to take tests and *pass the year*, regardless of whether they had learned anything. The condition of logical interpretation applied: if they passed it is because they learned, and if they learned, they know the content of the subjects.

In this regard, Machado (1999) already drew the attention of authorities and educators to the consequences of the lack of political commitment on the part of the government and the poor quality of education offered to the people at that time. For her,

Denying the vast majority of the population broad access to reading, due to the lack of a consistent policy to promote books and encourage literature, is equivalent to an act of arbitrariness by the authorities in power, against those who are not in a position to defend themselves, even out of ignorance of what is being denied to them. In the case of books, the failure to defend the right to reading through concrete measures ends up being a form of oppression. (...) What bothers, what makes one think, what disturbs, what has a critical meaning is eliminated. And with that, what should be food for the spirit is transformed into mere chewing gum, without any nutritional contribution (MACHADO, 1999, pp. 74 and 75).

Therefore, parents, teachers and caregivers must remember that, at any time, access to Culture, be it literature, sculpture, painting, theater, cinema, Folklore, guarantees the integral development: intellectual, human and spiritual, of children and adolescents. Further on, the same author launches the following provocation:

What kind of society do we want? An exclusionary and unfair conglomeration? A ghetto that reserves literature only for the initiated who inherit it from their parents or from some good schools and who will be able to form the questions of the future? Or a democratic society that considers access to literature as a basic and inalienable right of the citizen and begins to look at the quality of what is read with the same attention that it dedicates to reading statistics? (MACHADO, 1999, p. 101).

Today's society is already home to a range of individuals known as '*neither-nors*', who neither study nor work, and run the risk of being lured into marginalization and detours. They

are trapped in the mass media, addicted to electronic games, promiscuity, consuming trash culture, devoid of meaning and human values, and being consumed by alienation.

Boorstin (1914-2004 *apud* Machado, 1999) argues that

Electronic media can traverse space, but not time, (...) chronological myopia. (...) Reading the history of humanity is the only chance we have today to understand and recognize our past, which includes perversities, sadness and oppressions such as the Holocaust and the Inquisition, and to transcend evil without giving in to religious fanaticism (MACHADO, 1999, p. 111).

Here, a dilemma becomes evident: 'What kind of History is being taught in schools around the world? It is believed that it is not the true one, because wars, exploitation, injustices, fanaticism, violence, lack of love, addictions, excessive consumption, and uncontrolled exploitation of natural resources are increasingly present in the world. This is the type of routine present in educational institutions: people study to take tests, pass the year and forget the didactic content, and not to learn and have a dignified human formation. This happens because the didactic content is devoid of Science and Art; it is just didactic content. If the truth of the past were explored in the correct way, it is believed that man would think twice before committing violence, since it compromises the existence of future generations.

In this same vein, Birkerts (1925-2017 *apud* Machado, 1999) drew attention to the following issue regarding technological advances: "The premises and assumptions that operated in our society no longer work, are no longer valid. The historical transition to electronic culture was too sudden and threw us into unknown terrain. We lost moral and psychological reference points (1999, p. 114).

This statement explains a lot. Since then, humanity has been in decline and, today, the notions of morality, values, spirituality, honesty, mutual respect, apathy, love, among so many values, have given way to competition, narcissism, individualism and selfishness, unbridled competition, lack of limits, promiscuity, addictions, immediacy, consumerism, among others, which makes social coexistence increasingly worn out.

In the meantime, individuals are faced every day with a chaotic world in which values are inverted, cultures devoid of meaning are valued and applauded, and truth and authenticity are disregarded. The situation is so compromised that people can no longer even believe the faces they meet. Lip and facial fillers, silicone implants, and plastic surgery are leaving people without their essence and identity. The beauty industry is dictating the rules, and those who lack critical thinking consume this chaos without questioning it. Authenticity, ethics, morals, and

respect are lost amidst this flood of information and misinformation. Humans have succumbed to their unruly lies, and technology has advanced to the point of overthrowing its creator.

Next, Machado lists the losses and gains of postmodernity for the individual in broad generalizations.

Earnings :

1. An increase in the global perspective, admitting the complexity of interrelationships.
2. The expansion of the capacity of neurons, allowing them to simultaneously accommodate a large number of stimuli.
3. A relative understanding of situations, allowing the eradication of old prejudices and tending towards tolerance.
4. A willingness to try new situations.

Losses :

1. A fragmented sense of time, affecting the experience of duration and depth.
2. A reduction in the ability to concentrate and a general impatience with prolonged searches.
3. A shaking of the belief in narratives and grand theories based on narratives (such as those of Christ, Marx and Freud) that previously shaped subjective experience.
4. A divorce from the past and the meaning of history as a cumulative and organic process.
5. A feeling of estrangement from one's own geographical place and community.
6. An absence of any strong vision of a personal or collective future.
7. A shrinking of the individual and autonomous sphere. (MACHADO, Ana Maria, 1999.p.115)

Every day, we witness the results of losses, with people lost in time, there is more agitation and immediacy; Christ, like many theorists and their philosophical, sociological and anthropological principles, has already been forgotten; there is fragmentation of the information that is conveyed in schools and in the mass media; with people without a sense of their place in the world, who live in a city, a state, a country, a continent, in the northern region, literally, in the southern hemisphere; individuals who live without dreams and without perspective in life; there is similarity in the behavior and attitudes of people in different places, resulting from the consumption of mass and alienated information conveyed by the media.

It is clear that citizens live under orders, working, consuming and having fun with what is offered to them, in the way they are allowed. Anesthetized, individuals belonging to different social classes behave as determined by the consumer market. They celebrate the same dates, behave in the same way, have fun when they are told to have fun, wear clothes like uniforms, follow what fashion dictates. They live in fear of being criticized for not accepting certain

dictates; in short, they have lost their authenticity, their unique way of being and thinking; that which makes them human, all too human.

Here, it is worth remembering an excerpt from the fable *If Sharks Were Men*, by Bertold Brecht:

Furthermore, if sharks were men, the equality that exists today among the small fish would also end; some of them would obtain positions and be placed above the others. Those who were a little bigger could even eat the smaller ones, which would only be pleasing to the sharks; because, in this way, they themselves would more constantly obtain larger bites to devour and the larger small fish that would hold the positions would be worth the order among the small fish so that they would become teachers, officers, engineers in the construction of boxes and so on. Concise and Considerable, only then would there be civilization in the sea (BRECHT, 2006, sp).

The criticism posed by the essayist is the same as always, especially the one that emerged with the *Enlightenment*, first that civilization only exists if the precepts are in accordance with the positivist canonical rule and following the Cartesian primer; nothing outside of this can even be thought of as something human and worthy of being considered as something close to natural development. This leads humans to desire a type of existence that does not fit the species, believing that by achieving it they will have all the time necessary and desired to enjoy their spaces of happiness and well-being.

The creation of AI follows this principle, in which things will be solved more quickly and accurately, leaving humanity free to make decisions in other areas. However, this is an obtuse thought, because situations do not occur in a linear manner, much less the conditions for resolution, which often require detailed analysis, even offering the option of non-intervention, a decision that would be impossible for an automaton, since it is programmed to act towards conflict resolution; not to analyze its ethical and psychological dimensions and the impacts of these on the future of those involved.

In the health field, things are even more complex, because a medical consultation depends on a rigorous anamnesis, conducted by a professional who knows the details to be explored regarding the patient's memory; sometimes having to resort to inference techniques to ensure that the patient is reporting the events with maximum precision. It is not about interpreting clinical laboratory tests and prescribing medications according to the symptoms. In the case of surgical intervention, this is another turning point; because it is not about being precise in the cutting and extraction of tumors and dead tissue; this is a decision that must be made during the operation, which may or may not be to remove them, and this is a technical

decision based on professional experience gained through clinical practice and not the result of years of study or automatic programming.

Only the study and systematic analysis of the actions that are being transferred to AI as if they were *skills*, and one of humanity's worst cognitive problems has always been its extremely limited ability to interpret the terms presented to it. They treat everything as a given and determined end, not seeking to understand what nuances are inserted in each component, and the aforementioned term encompasses a dimension that not even the most intelligent machine or even the most intellectualized human being can fit into, including professionals in specific areas with established careers.

Human intelligence develops through contact with other humans, through the symbolic exchange of experiences and through direct experimentation of such experiences, whether individually or collectively; knowledge or wisdom cannot be transferred to anyone simply by reading texts or through reports of experiences. With machines, this transfer occurs through data records that, at most, follow a protocolled, rigid order and without any conditions for adjustments in the route or decision-making in the middle of the process.

BUT, AFTER ALL, WHAT IS ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE?

This is a question that could be very easy to answer, if the answer were objective; but, it is not about saying that it is a type of action that responds to automated commands, through situation analysis, because it is not! According to Asth (snt), “(artificial intelligence) is a field of application and research in computing, which deals with means (systems and programs) capable of performing tasks previously only possible by humans. AI can be defined as the ability of machines to replicate natural intelligence”.

This condition posed by this gentleman already shows his ignorance about what human intelligence is and its conditions of manifestation, as well as the fact that he does not even know the concept of Artificial Intelligence. An automaton, at most, can reproduce, imperfectly, human *behavior*; never its intelligence, since this is the expression of creativity and a machine cannot create anything; only reproduce.

This technology is already used in online shopping and advertising, web searches, digital personal assistants, automatic translations, smart homes, cities and infrastructures, cars, cybersecurity, artificial intelligence against COVID-19, combating disinformation, among others. Once again, we are faced with a conundrum, because how can something that is unable to analyze and interpret information logically and circumstantially, without the slightest

possibility of contextualizing the causal links that connect it to facts and individuals, say whether it is true or false?

In this context, as in times past, few will benefit from this invention in private, for example, having a car that moves by itself, an autonomous house, more precise medical exams, among others, and the majority will benefit from it collectively, consuming products such as energy, food, industrialized products, security, among others, resulting from the applicability of AI.

Given the above, several questions arise: is humanity prepared to live with AI? If ethical values are distorted, what will prevent the indiscriminate use of AI to increasingly exploit the shady interests of large corporations? Until now, computers and cell phones worked according to the commands for which they were programmed, and from now on, with this technology, nothing is programmed by human action? Has AI achieved a supposed cognitive autonomy, like a human being, who thinks and acts alone? However, the difference between the intellectual capacity of man and that of a machine is very different, is the reasoning of a machine much faster and more precise than that of a human? Is it possible that AI will dominate humanity at some point? If anyone is willing to believe this, it will be the machines that will give up dominating humanity; because in a very short time, humans will cause the entire system to collapse, because automatons will not be able to program human individuals to follow automatic orders.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

For better or worse, this is the result of technological advancement, AI (Artificial Intelligence) and, like all human inventions, the path to be followed depended on the thinking and intention of the human controlling the systems. In a world that is constantly advancing and improving aspects of energy development, it is a fact that one day we will be able to come close to creating controls with a very objective response capacity to the interests of reducing time and optimizing results.

Human beings are endowed with multiple feelings, have the ability to feel compassion, to love, to set limits, to live together, to interact, to feel empathy, to smile, to cry, to pray, to call, to dream, to plan and, above all, they carry with them memories of their past, secrets, sensitivities, which, even though they live among the masses, have a touch of being unique. After all, no one feels joy or sadness in the same way as another. Furthermore, there is, in a few

cases, the spark of divine creation, which, according to spirituality, makes them human, different from other creatures.

Now, as there is no human being aware of their ethical duty behind this machine that is supposedly capable of reasoning and making decisions, we can only hope that political, academic and large technology corporation authorities, the so-called *Bigtechs*, do not manipulate them, as they do with children, to serve a privileged few, while enslaving and keeping the majority in their mental cages.

The great challenge is to make humans question their positions in the universe, as those who hold the power to change the course of history or keep it as it is. Delegating and, at the same time, relegating one's own future to automated machines, as if this were something worthy of praise and enthusiasm, means having to accept the idea that humanity has reached its lowest point of expectation and also of vanity, in which a mechanical creation of man will decide whether or not it exists, becoming *more* competent than its creator, surpassing all the professionals who dedicated years of their respective lives to creating and applying knowledge and understanding the systems so that they could make the wisest decisions in their respective fields of activity.

REFERENCES

ASTH, Rafael C. *Artificial Intelligence (AI): what it is, its types and how it works*. Available at: <https://www.todamateria.com.br/inteligencia-artificial/>. Accessed on 07/06/2024.

BRECHT Bertold. *Stories of Mr. Keuner*. São Paulo: Editora 34, 2006. (If Sharks Were Men). [Work originally published in Germany in 2004].

CHAIMOWICZ, Luiz; CAMPOS, Mário. *Us and the Robots*. Available at <https://brasilecola.uol.com.br/informatica/robos.htm>. Accessed July 1, 2024.

CUNHA, Maria Antonieta Antunes. *Children's Literature. Theory and Practice*. São Paulo: Ática, 1997.

MACHADO, Ana Maria. *Against the Current : Conversation on Reading and Politics*. São Paulo: Ática, 1999.

RICARDO, Cassiano. *Jeremiah without crying*. Rio de Janeiro: José Olympio, 1976. [Work originally published in 1964].

SILVA, Ezequiel Theodoro da. *With Open Eyes: Reflections on the Development of Reading in Brazil*. São Paulo: Ática, 1991.